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“HOW CAN SOCIAL MEDIA MAKE HISTORY?”

Today's generation has been so fascinating with different technologies including the varied social media sites in the world. As I ponder, “How can we make use the best of this media?” There were some studies that would discuss the evolution of the media and the great examples to illustrate the way social media has changed. As I watched Clay Shirkey's videos, he uses historical information to describe the transition of media that started some 500 years ago.

I, as a member of the so-called Generation X, personally agree with Clay's statement that technologies now offer more opportunities and allow people to become active producers and dispensers of pieces of information. Everyone has become participants in disseminating information that we gather from the internet. All of us are guilty of this. I am guilty of this by sharing useful posts on my Facebook timeline LOL! Netizens have become instant journalists of their own. Everyone is a look-out especially in terms of politics. But there are tendencies that we are losing some quality in the information we receive. A lot of fake news and ridiculous ideas are spread like wildfire out of nowhere. In the world of politics, throwing shits to their opponent is quite normal. This is to gain people's trust especially during elections. Politicians take advantage of social media by attacking their enemies' weaknesses, dragging their enemies down by making up stories, it may be fake or true, no one could ever tell. Another good point is that in terms of calamities, social media is truly helpful. The latest earthquake in Greece that happened last February 11, 2025, and some other recently natural calamities make a good example of how social media can make history. I find it really amazing how netizens spread the news quickly. It was quite a shame to the professionals or authorized reporters that they found the news later after several minutes that the earthquake had occurred. Through social media, the news reached worldwide and after a day, donations had arrived. Can you see how social media works? It is amazing how people from other parts of the world can respond quickly to countries that are in need. Of course, it was made possible by the SOCIAL MEDIA! Now, what truly concerns me is our youth. It is our responsibility as elders to guide the young ones in using social media as we all know there are a lot of crimes happening today in our society. If we fail to guide the young ones, their future will

be at stake or worse is their lives. They are vulnerable and are receptive to information they just find on the internet.

Overall, I am fascinated with how social media helps and improves the lives of people. Let's just look at social media in a favorable light despite its disadvantages because they could inform and help situations such as the different natural calamities and its causes. Being responsible and using our common sense are important parts in embracing these innovations.

